

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR AND FAILURE CRITERIA OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS UNDER STATIC AND DYNAMIC LOADING

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SUMMARY

The quasi-static and dynamic behavior of two composite materials was characterized and failure theories were developed/expanded to describe static and dynamic failure under multi-axial states of stress. A recently developed interfiber/interlaminar failure theory was shown to be in excellent agreement with experimental results.

Keywords: Multi-axial testing, dynamic behaviour, strain rate effects, failure envelopes, dynamic failure theory

INTRODUCTION

Composite naval structures have many advantages over more conventional ones including stealth, insulation, lower manufacturing cost, low maintenance and corrosion resistance. Specific applications depend on the type of ship, part of the ship (topside, hull, bulkheads, etc.), mission and anticipated environment. Surface and submersible naval structures are subject to a variety of threats including mines, air and underwater explosions, and to other types of dynamic loadings including blast loading and wave-slamming. Such loadings are typically highly transient and the structural and material response occurs over very short (dynamic) time scales of the order of milliseconds or microseconds.

To mitigate such mission threats it is important to understand the basic material behavior under similar conditions and to design materials, structures, and systems that make such mitigation feasible and effective. For example, it is important to determine material behavior at very high strain rates, encountered under blast loading, and to analyze and design new structural concepts that optimize the material/structural response. Understanding the failure mechanisms of materials and structures in a dynamic loading environment is a prerequisite toward enhancing protection and survivability of both personnel and structure/equipment inside naval ships.

The goal of the current research is to gain a better understanding of the mechanics of aerospace and marine structures made of composite materials, to provide guidelines and criteria for material selection and design of such structures. The approach followed was to characterize the quasi-static and dynamic behavior of composite materials and develop/expand failure theories to describe static and dynamic failure under multi-axial states of stress.

QUASI-STATIC CHARACTERIZATION

Materials

The materials investigated are unidirectional glass/vinylester, and carbon/epoxy (AS4/3501-6). The first one consists of unidirectional E-glass fibers stabilized with transverse Kevlar fibers (Hexcel 1842). The second material is reinforced with a four-harness satin weave glass fabric (style 120 E-glass, Fibre Glast). The matrix was vinyl ester resin 1110 (Fibre Glast) cured with 1 wt% MEKP (Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide). The carbon/epoxy material was obtained in prepreg form and laminates were prepared by the standard autoclave process. The glass/vinylester composite was processed into laminates by a Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) process.

Testing and Results

Multi-axial experiments were performed by testing off-axis prismatic specimens, primarily in compression. Stress-strain curves were obtained for unidirectional glass/vinylester under compression at various loading directions with respect to the principal fiber reinforcement. Two to six specimens were tested in each case. A typical stress-strain curve is shown in Figure 1. This curve like those for different load orientations, shows highly nonlinear behavior and exhibits a plateau with some strain softening. Results of initial axial modulus, strength, and normal and shear components at failure are tabulated in Table 1. Similar stress-strain curves were obtained for the carbon/epoxy composite.

Figure 1. Stress-strain curves of unidirectional glass/vinylester composite under compression at various orientations

Table 1. Properties of Unidirectional E-Glass/Vinylester under Off-Axis Compression

Load Orientation θ (deg)	Axial Modulus E_x (GPa)	Axial Strength F_{xc} (MPa)	Normal Stress at Failure σ_2 (MPa)	Shear Stress at Failure τ_6 (MPa)
30	16.4	117	-29	50
45	10.8	103	-52	52
60	10.4	106	-80	46
90	11.0	99	-99	0

FAILURE ANALYSIS (QUASI-STATIC)

The results obtained were evaluated based on classical failure criteria, noninteractive criteria (maximum stress, maximum strain), fully interactive criteria (Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu), and failure mode based and partially interactive criteria (Hashin-Rotem, Sun, and Daniel) [1-7]. The latter is primarily applicable to interfiber/interlaminar failure and is expressed in the form of three subcriteria:

Compression dominated failure:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{F_{2c}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_6}{F_{2c}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{E_2}{G_{12}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (\text{criterion NUa}) \quad (1)$$

Shear dominated failure:

$$\left(\frac{\tau_6}{F_6}\right)^2 + 2\frac{\sigma_2}{F_6} \frac{G_{12}}{E_2} = 1 \quad (\text{criterion NUb}) \quad (2)$$

Tension dominated Failure:

$$\frac{\sigma_2}{F_{2t}} + \left(\frac{\tau_6}{F_{2t}}\right)^2 \left(\frac{E_2}{2G_{12}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (\text{criterion NUc}) \quad (3)$$

For a composite with properties related as

$$F_6 = F_{2t} \left(\frac{2G_{12}}{E_2}\right) \quad (4)$$

or, equivalently

$$\varepsilon_{2t}^{ult} = \frac{\gamma_6^{ult}}{2} \quad (5)$$

the NUb and NUc criteria coincide with the Christensen criterion

$$\frac{\sigma_2}{F_{2t}} + \left(\frac{\tau_6}{F_6}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (6)$$

This condition is nearly satisfied for many unidirectional materials but usually not for woven fabric composites.

Figure 2 shows experimental results for the unidirectional glass/vinylester composite under transverse normal (compressive) and in-plane shear loading compared with predictions of various classical theories, including those by Sun [1], Christensen [2], and Daniel et al. (NU) theory based on local maximum strain criteria in the interfiber matrix [3-7]. In this case it may appear that a maximum stress criterion is as good as any other theory in predicting failure. It appears that for a wide range of biaxiality of compression and shear, the shear stress at failure remains nearly constant. A closer look at the failure modes reveals that for biaxial states with high in-plane shear, the compressive stress component in the fiber direction is high enough to cause early fiber microbuckling. Thus, theories based on the assumption of matrix dominated failure mechanisms (shear or tension) cannot adequately describe the observed behavior for this material.

Figure 2. Comparison of theoretical failure envelopes and experimental results for E-glass/vinylester composite under transverse compression and shear.

Figure 3 shows experimental results for a unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite under transverse normal (compressive) and in-plane shear loading compared with predictions of the same theories discussed before. Of all theories compared, the NU theory is in very good agreement with the experimental results.

DYNAMIC CHARACTERIZATION

The unidirectional glass/vinylester and carbon/epoxy composites were characterized under high strain rate conditions by means of a Hopkinson bar system as shown below in Fig. 4. Prismatic specimens were machined at various orientations to the principal fiber direction for off-axis testing (Fig. 5). Off-axis compression produces combinations of transverse compression and in-plane shear.

Figure 3. comparison of theoretical failure envelopes and experimental results for AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composite under transverse compression and shear.

Figure 4. Schematic of split hopkinson bar for compression testing at high strain rates

Figure 5. High strain rate off-axis compression testing of composite specimen

Dynamic stress-strain curves were obtained for the two materials mentioned before and compared with corresponding static ones. Figure 6 shows typical static and dynamic stress-strain curves for the unidirectional glass/vinylester composite for four loading orientations. Similar stress-strain curves were obtained for the unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite. Typical ones are shown in Figure 7 for four loading orientations.

Figure 6. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for glass/vinylester composite under compressive loading at various orientations with the fiber direction.

Figure 7. Static and dynamic stress-strain curves for unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite under compressive loading at various orientations with the fiber direction

FAILURE ANALYSIS (DYNAMIC)

Dynamic properties for the materials tested were analyzed in a similar way as the static properties by the same failure theories. The basic lamina properties, stiffnesses and strengths, in the theories were replaced with the equivalent dynamic ones. Figure 8 shows experimental results for the unidirectional glass/vinylester composite under transverse normal (compressive) and in-plane shear loading compared with predictions of the various theories discussed before. Although the case of static loading was somewhat obscured by failure mechanisms not totally accounted for by matrix behavior, in the case of high rate loading the matrix behaves in a more brittle manner. The NU theory [7] in this case is in very good agreement with the experimental results. Figure 9 shows a comparison between static and dynamic failure envelopes predicted by the NU theory and experimental results. It is seen that strain rate has a profound influence on the failure behavior of the material and that the NU theory can predict this behavior satisfactorily, especially in the dynamic case.

Figure 8. Comparison of theoretical failure envelopes and experimental results for glass/vinylester composite under dynamic transverse compression and shear.

Figure 9. Comparison of static and dynamic experimental results and failure envelopes predicted by the NU theory for the glass/vinylester composite.

Similar results were obtained for the unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite. Figure 10 shows experimental results for this composite under transverse normal (compressive) and in-plane shear loading compared with predictions of the various theories discussed before. As in the case of static loading, the NU theory is in very good agreement with the experimental results. Figure 11 shows a comparison between static and dynamic failure envelopes predicted by the NU theory and experimental results. It is seen that strain rate has a profound influence on the failure behavior of the material and that the NU theory can predict this behavior satisfactorily for both the static and dynamic cases.

Figure 10. Comparison of theoretical failure envelopes and experimental results for carbon/epoxy composite under dynamic transverse compression and shear.

Figure 11. Comparison of static and dynamic experimental results and failure envelopes predicted by the NU theory for the carbon/epoxy composite.

CONCLUSION

Many computer codes are being developed for the analysis and design of naval vessels subjected to severe liquid blast and wave slamming in service. Material properties and appropriate failure theories under dynamic conditions are needed to implement these codes. The work described in this paper provides guidance and input for such analysis and design.

Two composite materials, a glass/vinylester and a carbon/epoxy composite, were characterized statically and under high strain rate loading at various biaxial states of stress combining transverse compression and shear. The previously developed failure theory at Northwestern University was extended to the dynamic loading regime and was shown to be in excellent agreement with experimental results.

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